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Research Article

**OBSERVANCE OF DURING THE FASTING WHAT FACTORES
MINIMIZES THE VITAMIN-D OBSERVANCE IF THE
METHODS THAT CAUSES OF THE MINIMIZATION OF THE
VITAMIN-D**¹Dr Aroosa Shabbir, ²Dr Maria Imran, ³Dr Sibgha Ahmed¹DHQ Hospital Pakpattan, ²BHU Budho, Taxila, ³Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore.**Article Received:** October 2020**Accepted:** November 2020**Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

The diabetes is a disease has the higher level of sugar and the insulin level. It is observed that the there is a two types called the type 1 diabetes and the type 2 diabetes. In the type 2 diabetes, patient start produces the minimization insulin. If the proper insulin is not productive then the proper glucose is not observed in the body which loss the energy of the patient. It is observed that the minimization of insulin becomes the reason is that due to the minimization of the beta cells. It is observed that the type 1 diabetes the patient losses its greater level of energy level. It is the great loss in the body. All the vitamins are the important role in our body. Vitamin-d also plays the important role in the body. It is responsible for the observance of calcium in the body. If the proper vitamin-d is not present in the body it lacks the proper observance of glucose in the body. Vitamin-d increases the strongness of the defense system. As you know that the if the body has the strong defense system then the defense system as enough to fight with the every disease. It is also in the case of the diabetes so the vitamin-d it's directly relates to the diabetes.

Keywords: type two diabetes, vitamin-d, minimization of vitamin-d, role of defense system, diabetes and vitamin-d.**Corresponding author:****Dr Aroosa Shabbir**

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QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

As you know that vitamins are most important chemical in our body. They play a very important role in the body. It is observed that it plays a role in the defense system. And it also plays a very important role in the proper observance of the calcium in the body. It also plays a very important role in the strength of our defense system if our defense system is strong it plays a role to fight with the every disease. It is observed that it directly relates to the diabetes. In this study we will observe that the what methods is used to run smoothly the vitamins. It is observed that if the patient have fast mean it does not take any food or drink from the morning and the diabetes both minimizes the important vitamin called the vitamin-d. In this study we will also know about that what the liver plays an important role in this. We will find the many expression through when the subject is in the position of the body. In this study it is revealed that the important part to run the vitamin-d in the smoothness. In this study the role of kidney is also involved what chemical it transfers then what happened to a body. In this study it is observed that the vitamin-d plays a very important role in the body. It is responsible for the proper observance of calcium in the body and it is also observed in this study that vitamins are important for our body. It is observed that the vitamin-d effects the two materials called the adipogenesis and the other called the adipocyte in the body. It is observed that if the bodies have the patient have the minimization of the vitamin-d it causes to a many diseases. Due to this minimization almost half of the world is covered.

METHODOLOGY:

In this study we started a study on the animals. This all study is approved by the Mayo Hospital Lahore. It is also approved by the local animals committee in the Mayo Hospital Lahore. It is observed that all animals were kept in place of the dark light cycle of the 12 hours a cycle. In this study after all the study the mice were died due to the CO₂ and then according to the next step the tissues will be collected so that the proper studied should be pertypeed. For this study all the male's mice obtained from the laboratory of the Mayo Hospital Lahore. All the males and mice have the age of the 6 to 13 weeks old and all the mice have fasting they have given the free water. It is observed that all the mice have the fasted from the all these except from the water. This experiment is pertypeed again and the again it is observed that all the results become same by again and again experimenting. All the animals are killed at the end due for the next experiment steps. In this study we injected the c57bl injection in the mice. In order to study the kidney part we used the mice that are 8 weeks old. We check it daily for 3 days and the after 12 hours. It is kept in eye that the mice that are males are injected with the dba 2 injections. In the mice whose them we injected the injection of the dba 2 we obtained the RNA from it. In this study we also obtained the sequences of the pcr primers according to their gene forward primer and the reverse primer as shows in the following table. Following table will show the forward primer reverse primer according to the genes as shows in the following figure.

Table 1 – Sequences of the PCR primers

Gene	Forward primer (5'-3')	Reverse primer (5'-3')
mPGC-1 α	GCAGGTCGAACGAACTGAC ^a	CTCAGCCTGGGAACACGTTA ^a
	TCCTCCTCATAAAGCCAACC ^b	GCCTTGGGTACCAGAACACT ^b
	CTGCTCTGGTTGGTGAGGA ^c	GCAGGCTCATTGTTGTAAGT ^c
	AGCCGTGACCACTGACAACGAG ^d	GCTGCATGGTTCTGAGTGCTAAG ^d
PEPCK	GGTGTACTGGGAAGGCATC	CAATAATGGGGCACTGGCTG
mERR α	ATCTGCTGGTGGTTGAACCTG	AGAAGCCTGGGATGCTCTTG
mCYCS	CCAAATCTCCACGGTCTGTTC	ATCAGGGTATCCTCTCCCCAG
mATP5B	GGTTCATCCTGCCAGAGACTA	AATCCCTCATCGAACTGGACG
mVDR	GAATGTGCCTCGGATCTGTGG	GGTCATAGCGTTGAAGTGGAA
rCYP2R1	AAACTACAACCAATGTGCTCCG	CTTCCAAGAAGGCCTCCTGT
18S	CGCCGCTAGAGGTGAAATTC	CCAGTCGGCATCGTTTATGG
TBP	GAATATAATCCAAGCGATTTG	CACACCATTTTCCAGAAGT
mPGC-1 β	CTCCAGGCAGGTTCAACCC	GGGCCAGAAGTTCCTTAGG
mGR	AGTCCCCCTGGTAGAGAC	GGTGAAGACGCAGAAACCTTG
mNR1D1	TCCCCAAGAGAGAGAAGCAA	CTGAGAGAAGCCCACCAAAG
mTAT	TGCTGGATGTTTCGCGTCAATA	CGGCTTACCTTCATGTTGTC
mGAPDH	GGTCATCATCTCCGCCCC	TTCTCGTGGTTACACCCATC
mG6PASE	CATCAATCTCCTCTGGGTGG	TGCTGTAGTAGTCGGTGTCC
mCYP2R1	Mm01159414_m1 (Life Technologies)	
mCYP24A1	Mm00487245_m1 (Life Technologies)	

RESULT:

This study had been pertypeed in the mayo hospital Lahore in which the result extracted in the mayo hospital Lahore. It is observed that the if the fasting and diabetes have the same time in the body is it minimizes the vitamin-d which is important for the proper observance of the calcium and the play an important role in the observance and the strongness of the defense system. If the defense system is strong it has an ability to defeat every single disease so it is shows that the vitamin-d is directly linked with the diabetes. For the purpose of this we pertypeed the study in the mayo hospital Lahore in this study we uses the mices all the mices are male and we kept in the dark cycle of 12 hours all the mices are keep fasting but we gave them a water. In the liver of the mices we have find a cyp2r1 expression in the liver of the mices. It is observed that the this chemical is its repressed in the rat liver. It is observed that the minimization observed in the 24 hours of the fasting. In the following figure it is shows that the fasting hours and the expression of the rna according to what time it changes in the body and this chemical works in the body. It is shows in following figure. In the

following figure it is shows that the plasma about protein and about the vitamin-d. As shows in the following figure.

DISCUSSION:

In this experiment we have to find the importance of vitamin-d and the diabetes is the diabetes and vitamin-d is any relationship between each other or not. For the purpose of this we pertypeed the study in the mayo hospital Lahore in this study we uses the mices all the mices are male and we kept in the dark cycle of 12 hours all the mices are keep fasting but we gave them a water. If the defense system is strong it has an ability to defeat every single disease so it is shows that the vitamin-d is directly linked with the diabetes. In this study it is kept in eye that the plasma will use to find the status of vitamin-d in our body. In the following figure part as it are shows that the RNA and the pepck and the cyp24a according to what changes exist in the body. In the part b we find the pgc and the pgc negative according to the RNA expression. As the following figure shows according to what result is obtained in the library of the Mayo hospital Lahore. As shows in the following figure.

CONCLUSION:

This all study is approved by the mayo hospital Lahore. It is also approved by the local animals committee in the mayo hospital Lahore. It is observed that the all animals were kept in place of the dark light cycle of the 12 hours a cycle. In this study after all the study the mice were died due to the co2 and then the according to the next step the tissues will be collected so that the proper studied should be pertypeed. For this study all the male's mice obtained from the laboratory of the mayo hospital

Lahore. We uses the mice all the mice are male and we kept in the dark cycle of 12 hours all the mice are keep fasting but we gave them a water. In the liver of the mice we have find a cyp2r1 expression in the liver of the mice. It is observed that the this chemical is its repressed in the rat liver. It is observed that the minimization observed in the 24 hours of the fasting. The following figure will show that the role of the liver according to the fasting in this study it is observed that the how the cyp2r1 and the pgc plays a role in this study. Following figure will show that

what the roles of it. How the liver of the mice acts

during the study.

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